

Implementing pedagogical translanguaging in trilingual schools

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 26 March 2020

Accepted 27 April 2020

Available online 3 May 2020

Keywords:

Translanguaging
Multilingual education
Minority languages
Trilingualism
Multilingualism

ABSTRACT

This article reports on a study of primary and secondary school teachers in Basque schools where Basque, Spanish and English are included in the curriculum. Traditionally, the three languages have been taught separately and the possible benefits of using the whole linguistic repertoire to establish links between the languages had not been acknowledged. New trends in multilingual education focusing on the whole linguistic repertoire and translanguaging have provided opportunities to change traditional approaches to teaching and to explore the potential advantages of translanguaging. In this study, a group of teachers from different trilingual schools were provided with theoretical and practical information about translanguaging and were asked to implement pedagogical translanguaging in their own class. Teachers were given a guideline for the implementation and were asked to prepare a lesson plan including activities that involved the use of two or more languages for pedagogical purposes. Then, the teachers taking part in this study used translanguaging for at least one lesson, received feedback from their students and reflected on the implementation. The results of this study show that pedagogical translanguaging can provide new opportunities for language learning and language awareness in the context of multilingual education.

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1. Introduction

The relationship between schools and society is bidirectional. The characteristics of society are reflected in schools in different ways. For example, the diversity of students' home languages in many countries nowadays reflects the diversity of society. At the same time, schools develop programs that are expected to influence the characteristics of the society in which they are located. In many cases the curriculum includes different languages, which can be both local and international, and the school aims at developing competencies in several languages. These situations call for pedagogies that promote flexibility between languages and the use of resources across those languages (May, 2013; Cenoz & Gorter, 2015).

In this article, pedagogical translanguaging is understood as planned by the teacher inside the classroom so that multilingual learners benefit from their whole linguistic repertoire (Cenoz, 2017; Cenoz & Gorter this issue). Pedagogical translanguaging softens boundaries between languages and aims at developing multilingualism and multiliteracy. Translanguaging practices can take many shapes, even when only focusing on practices that have been designed and planned

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by the teacher. In this study, translanguaging strategies are developed by language teachers and content teachers in a specific multilingual context. The description and analysis of the way teachers understand and implement translanguaging can contribute not only to developing these and other translanguaging practices in different contexts, but also to advancing theoretical approaches in the study of multilingual education in general and translanguaging in particular.

In this article, we first discuss pedagogical translanguaging as related to multilingual speakers, their whole linguistic repertoire and social context, and then we focus on its implementation in three schools.

2. Pedagogical translanguaging and multilingual speakers

Studies on third language acquisition have highlighted the differences between second and third language acquisition and the advantages of multilingualism in the acquisition of additional languages (Jessner & Cenoz, 2019; Safont Jordà, 2017). These advantages are usually linked to the broader linguistic repertoire of multilingual speakers and to the metalinguistic awareness and learning strategies they have developed in the process of acquiring previous languages (Cenoz, 2013). An example of these advantages that goes much further than third language acquisition is reported by Elka Todeva, who specializes in Applied Linguistics and who is an accomplished multilingual speaker (Todeva, 2009):

Knowing some Latin and Greek not only made thousands of English words semantically transparent to me but, as an added bonus, later I knew that I could risk using many of my Latin and Greek words in Spanish and Italian since they had already proven their transferability potential with English. Compare, for instance, philologia, agronomia, astronomia (Latin/Greek) with philology, agronomy, astronomy (English), with philologia (Italian), filología (Spanish), agronomía (Spanish), agronomia (Italian). As a multilingual, I was getting many such “free rides” and was empowered significantly. I was in a position to activate word formation patterns in my mental lexicon after minimal exposure. Having developed an eye for recognizing slight variations, I did not need much input to figure out, for instance, that the Spanish suffix ~ción is quite similar to the English ~tion, or that the Spanish ~miento more or less corresponds to ~ment in English and ~mento in Italian.

As an expert in Applied Linguistics, Elka Todeva can reflect on the process of using her linguistic repertoire and develop strategies to acquire new words in Spanish and Italian. The languages that she identifies as useful in her repertoire are Latin and Greek but mainly when specific words in these languages had already been successfully transferred to English, which is the language she learned first. Another interesting point in this quotation is that Todeva has developed “an eye for recognizing slight variations”. This means that she uses a strategy based on her prior knowledge to the acquisition of Spanish and Italian. This strategy can advance her acquisition of vocabulary by focusing on suffixes and indicates a high level of metalinguistic awareness, which can be associated with her training as an applied linguist. This example shows how new languages can share features with some of the languages in the multilingual speaker’s repertoire and how the learning process can be understood as adjusting the multilingual repertoire to accommodate for an additional language. Elka Todeva acknowledges that she gets “free rides” because of her multilingualism.

Nowadays, we have students with rich linguistic trajectories in many schools. There is a diversity of home languages and there are also programs that aim at developing multilingual competences in several languages. Multilingual speakers have the potential to benefit from their repertoire, but their metalinguistic awareness and strategy development may not be as advanced as Elka Todeva’s. In fact, it has been reported that multilinguals miss some opportunities at times. For example, Naggy et al. (1993) and Leonet, Cenoz, and Gorter (2020) reported that multilingual students failed to associate words in English and Spanish even if they were cognates. One of the reasons for this may be that traditional teaching has kept languages isolated from each other, so multilingual speakers have not been given sufficient opportunity to benefit from the advantages of their own multilingualism.

Cenoz and Gorter (2011, 2014) proposed the need to “Focus on Multilingualism” in teaching and research. They highlighted the importance of looking at students as multilingual speakers who are different from monolingual speakers and have rich linguistic trajectories. They also consider the need to look at the whole linguistic repertoire and to establish synergies between the different languages. The third dimension of “Focus on Multilingualism” is the social context. This includes the specific context of the school and the wider context in the community. “Focus on Multilingualism” regards multilingual trajectories as dynamic and highlights the resources which the multilingual learner has at his/her disposal. Pedagogical translanguaging is closely linked to this multilingual approach to teaching because it uses the multilingual speaker’s resources to enhance language and content learning. In pedagogical translanguaging, the multilingual repertoire is activated in order to support language acquisition and metalinguistic reflection.

The importance of the multilingual repertoire and the use of students’ resources was already mentioned in the CEFR (Council of Europe, 2001) but it is highlighted in the more recently published Companion volume (Council of Europe, 2018: 27): *In the reality of today’s increasingly diverse societies, the construction of meaning may take place across languages and draw upon user/learners’ plurilingual and pluricultural repertoires.* The CEFR Companion has developed specific scales for plurilingual comprehension that include concepts such as exploiting similarities among languages or exploiting parallel sources in different languages (p. 160). These concepts can be considered as pedagogical translanguaging practices.

The implementation of pedagogical translanguaging that is reported here is also linked to several of the goals in “Teaching to learn content and language through translanguaging” identified by García and Li (2014: 120). Goal number 4 is particularly relevant: “For cross-linguistic metalinguistic awareness so as to strengthen the students’ ability to meet the communicative exigencies of the socioeducational situation” and uses strategies such as “Word walls, sentence starters, cognates, comparing multilingual texts, multilingual vocabulary inquiry, and multilingual syntax/morphology inquiry”.

The use of cross-linguistic resources based on the students' whole multilingual repertoire has been associated with positive results in different contexts (Arteagoitia & Howard, 2015; Cummins, 2007, 2017; Lin, 2015; Lyster, Quiroga, & Ballinger, 2013). However, as García and Lin (2017) explain, it is still difficult for teachers to accept translanguaging because of the strong tradition of language separation ideologies. This article will detail the implementation of pedagogical translanguaging in a context where three languages have traditionally been taught separately. The implementation of pedagogical translanguaging has been designed and carried out by teachers themselves. In the next section, we will explain the context of the implementation.

3. The context

A group of in-service teachers from different primary and secondary multilingual schools attended a professional development course consisting of a combination of lectures and practical tasks (see also Gorter & Arocena, this issue). The course had an intensive face-to-face part, a theoretical part (20 h) and an online part (7 weeks) in which they participated while they were teaching. In this article, we focus on the implementation of a translanguaging session, which was carried out by teachers in their schools while they were following the online part of the course. All the teachers were working in the Basque Autonomous Community in Spain and were fluent in Basque and Spanish. As the course was in English, most teachers were teaching either English or an additional subject through the medium of English. Here, we focus on the implementation of translanguaging sessions in three classes: a science class taught in English in primary school and two English language classes in secondary school.

Basque is the main language of instruction in the Basque Autonomous Community, where the dominant language in society is Spanish (Gorter, Zenotz, Etxague, & Cenoz, 2014). Basque can be considered a minority language in its own territory and is spoken by approximately 34% of the population. Language isolation and monolingual ideologies have traditionally been associated with the preservation and revival of Basque and some Basque speakers are afraid of translanguaging because they think that it can only benefit Spanish, the majority language. Cenoz and Gorter (2017) explain that in the context of minority languages such as Basque, pedagogical translanguaging can be beneficial but that there is the need to allocate some "breathing spaces" for the exclusive use of the minority language. In the schools where the translanguaging experiences reported here were developed, Basque was the main language of instruction and pedagogical translanguaging was implemented in English or English-medium classes so Basque had plenty of "breathing spaces". However, the status of Basque as a minority language and the concern about taking away some space from the minority language can still be found, as will be seen below (see also Leonet, Cenoz, & Gorter, 2017).

The course and the specific experience of pedagogical translanguaging reported in this article meets the core characteristics of pedagogical translanguaging as defined by Cenoz and Gorter (this issue):

Type of program: All programs in the Basque Autonomous Community can be classed as multilingual education because they include three languages in the curriculum and their objective is multilingualism and multiliteracy in Basque, Spanish and English, both in primary and secondary education.

Aims: The translanguaging experiences reported here aim at developing language competences and in some cases academic content related to other school subjects.

Organization: Translanguaging activities are specifically planned by the teacher who has prepared a lesson plan in advance.

Approach: The boundaries between languages are soft. There are three languages used in the session and there is a designated main language, which in this case is English. Teachers are flexible regarding the use of the three languages or other languages during the class.

In-service teachers were provided with a guideline for the implementation of pedagogical translanguaging and were asked to prepare a lesson plan including activities that involved the use of two or more languages for pedagogical purposes. Then, the teachers taking part in this study used translanguaging for at least one lesson and they also got feedback from their students and reflected on the implementation. The whole process of the implementation lasted six weeks and was organized as follows:

Weeks 1-2. Preparation. The teachers, who had already completed the face-to-face sessions on "Focus on Multilingualism" and translanguaging as well as several tasks based on readings and discussions, received information about implementation. They could look at examples of pedagogical translanguaging and discuss their views in a forum with other teachers. The main aim of this stage was to develop ideas about how the translanguaging session in their own class would be planned.

Week 3. Lesson plan. The aim of this stage was to prepare and submit a lesson plan of the pedagogical translanguaging session. The teachers were given a template that covered the following sections: background information (subject, grade, number of students), the objectives, organization and materials for the translanguaging session, and information about the teaching unit in which the translanguaging session was going to be inserted. They also had to give a detailed description and timing of the different activities in the translanguaging session and explain how the session would be assessed.

Weeks 4 and 5. Implementation. The minimum time for the implementation of pedagogical translanguaging was one class, but teachers could also decide to have more sessions. Two weeks were given to make sure schools with different activities (outings, exams periods, etc) could be accommodated. The implementation of the lesson plan designed by the teacher also included an assessment regarding the objectives and feedback from the students. The template for language assessment included questions on the degree of difficulty of the implementation, students' progress, the teacher's motivation to include more pedagogical translanguaging sessions in the future and the perception the teacher had of other teachers in the same

school about the possibility of implementing pedagogical translanguaging in other classes. Teachers were also asked to get feedback from students by asking them questions about the degree of difficulty, their progress and if they perceived that the languages in their linguistic repertoire supported one another.

Week 6. Report and participation in a forum. Teachers submitted a report, which was based on the template of the lesson plan, adding information about the implementation and assessment process. They also shared their experience with other teachers by sending a post to an online forum.

This paper presents three cases that illustrate different ways pedagogical translanguaging can be used in the classroom. The experiences were carried out in three different schools.

3.1. School 1. using cognates in science

Background information. This translanguaging experience took place in the 6th year of primary education with students who were 11–12 years old. The school is a public primary school and the main language of instruction is Basque. English is also used as an additional language of instruction and Spanish is a school subject. The teacher has several years of experience teaching the three languages, mathematics and science. She is motivated and thinks that languages are very important. The teacher has planned to incorporate pedagogical translanguaging into two lessons with a focus on cognates in Basque, Spanish and English in a science class, which she usually teaches through the medium of English. The class has 21 students.

Aim of pedagogical translanguaging. The teacher considers that by working with cognates in the three languages, students will become aware of the way their first language can be useful when trying to understand an academic text in English. The lessons aim to improve vocabulary building and reading comprehension.

3.2. Structure of the sessions

Part 1. Listening and reading. The class starts with a pre-reading activity in which the teacher tries to elicit words related to the digestive system that students already know. Then, students listen to a text on the digestive system in English from their textbook. Afterwards, the students read the same text and answer some comprehension questions.

Part 2. Identifying cognates on a text. Once students have read the text, the teacher divides the class into groups of three to five students and asks them to identify cognates of English, Basque and Spanish words by filling in a chart given by the teacher. The instruction given is: “You can write the words with a similar appearance in the two or three languages in this chart here. Words with a similar appearance in the three languages are called cognates”. The chart gives an example, “digestive system”, in the three languages: “digestive system”, “sistema digestivo” and “digestion sistema”. Once the students have finished filling in the chart, the teacher helps the different groups to identify more cognates and asks students to discuss what cognates are and how they can be helpful. The teacher helps the different groups by asking questions so as to raise student awareness. The questions she asks are the following: *Which words did you find the most helpful to understand the text? Can Spanish words or Basque words be helpful when trying to understand a text in English? Can you think of any other different cognates?*

Part 3. Watching a video. This activity takes place with the whole class, not in groups. It is a video from the collection “How the body works” by Kidshealth. It lasts 5.08 min and it is called “How the digestive system works”. The video, which can be found on YouTube, is in English with subtitles in English and is part of an animated video series featuring the characters, Chloe and Nurb. Students are asked to write down the words that can have cognates in Spanish and/or Basque. They watch the video twice.

Part 4. Wordwall with cognates and pictures. The students are organized into groups again and prepare wordwalls with cognates and pictures. They use coloured cards so as to have the same colour for the words in each of the languages. The wordwalls are displayed in the classroom.

Part 5. Follow-up activity. One week later, students are asked to identify cognates in a text again to make sure they understand the concept of a cognate.

3.3. Feedback from school 1

The teacher answered some questions to evaluate the pedagogical translanguaging experience and also received feedback from students, as can be seen in the following summaries:

1. *Difficulty.* Students found the activities quite easy.
2. *Teacher's feeling.* The teacher did not encounter any difficulties because the students could adapt very easily, even though the activity was in three languages.
3. *Students' behavior and understanding of the activities.* The behavior was good but some groups did not work very hard. In general, they were motivated because it was different from other classes. They understood the activity without any problems. The teacher thinks that the students felt proud that they could demonstrate their knowledge of the three languages.

4. *Learning using multilingual activities.* The teacher reports that there was a difference because more attention was paid to language than in other science classes. Students realized that the knowledge of one language could help when learning other languages and when learning new content. They had to read the text and analyze what they were reading more carefully.
5. *Using pedagogical translanguaging in the future.* The teacher thinks she will use pedagogical translanguaging in the future and that she will extend it to other areas beyond cognates.
6. *Readiness of other teachers in your school to use pedagogical translanguaging.* According to the teacher, they would be ready if they received some training, and they could see the advantages. Otherwise, many teachers might see this approach as harmful for the Basque language. The teacher thinks that training is necessary for all teachers who are interested in implementing pedagogical translanguaging in their classes.

This school has implemented pedagogical translanguaging, with the teacher following the examples of cognates given in the professional development course but adapting them to the science course material. Another interesting point is that even though Basque is the main language at school, the teacher is aware of the concern about the potential risk of translanguaging for the Basque language and the need to provide specific professional development courses to implement pedagogical translanguaging. In general, it can be said that the experience was positive and that students paid more attention to language in the science class.

3.4. School 2. learning English grammar

Background information. The translanguaging experience reported here took place in a semi-private school that combines pre-primary, primary and secondary education in the same building. The school is subsidized by the government though there is still a small fee to be paid by the parents. The pedagogical translanguaging intervention took place in the English language class of the 3rd year of secondary education with students who are 14–15 years old. The main language of instruction is Basque but English is also an additional language of instruction for social sciences. Students study Spanish only as a school subject and French is an optional subject in secondary school. The teacher has over 20 years of experience teaching languages, mainly English, Basque and French. She is motivated and likes languages very much. The situation is different from the previous school because there are only three participants. They are Spanish-speaking immigrants from Latin American countries who have a low level of Basque and English. The remaining students in the class are completing other tasks while the teacher gives full attention to the three immigrant students in what can be considered a remedial class.

Aim of pedagogical translanguaging. The aim is to develop syntactic awareness by comparing syntactic features of the three languages. The lesson also aims at showing how Spanish as a first language can help to learn English and Basque.

3.5. Structure of the sessions

The activities are designed for one English language class.

3.6. The multilingual postcard

This is a text of 150 words in English. It is a postcard that one friend is sending to another. The text is divided into seven parts so as to include translations into Spanish and Basque after each of the parts. Reading the multilingual postcard is the first activity and the language used in the postcard is the basis for the exercises that follow.

Exercise: Identifying similar structures in the three languages. The three students are given a chart in which to write some expressions and structures that are underlined in the three languages. Students only have to write down the parts of the sentences that are underlined and the idea is that they pay attention to and compare the different expressions and structures.

Exercise: Comparison of sentence subjects in the three languages. Some of the expressions that have to be identified in the previous exercise are discussed by the teacher so as to draw attention to the compulsory use of the subject in English sentences but not in Spanish and Basque sentences, as can be seen in this example:

How are you? ¿Cómo estás? (tú) Zer moduz zaude? (zu)

After explaining this difference, students are asked to find other examples in the sentences that have been highlighted in the multilingual postcard in order to reach the conclusion that subjects are compulsory in English sentences but can be omitted in Basque and Spanish sentences. Students then complete another exercise in which they have to match nine short sentences in each of the three languages so as to reinforce the compulsory use of the subject in English. An example of this exercise is the sentence “They read a lot”. Students are given a selection of sentences and are asked to find the one which corresponds to the sentence “Leen mucho” in Spanish and “Asko irakurtzen dute” in Basque. In this exercise, the sentences are given but they are not in order, so students have to find the Spanish and Basque sentences that match the English ones.

Exercise: Subjects and auxiliary verbs in the multilingual postcard. In this exercise, students are asked to find other sentences (with subjects) in the multilingual postcard. These must be sentences that were not originally underlined. Here, the main point is to pay attention to the verbs in sentences such as “Two little girls are walking their dogs”. Then, in an additional

exercise, the sentences identified have to be turned into the interrogative and negative forms. The last exercise in the unit has four sentences that have to be turned into the negative and interrogative forms in the three languages, paying attention to the use of auxiliary verbs.

3.7. Feedback from school 2

1. *Difficulty.* The teacher thinks that the postcard may have been too long and the exercises were too difficult for the students to complete on their own. However, the students think the multilingual postcard was easy because it was in the three languages.
2. *Teacher's feeling.* The teacher found the session quite challenging, though the main problem was not related to translanguageing but to the fact that she had to devote all her attention to the three students while the rest of the students were in the classroom doing other exercises.
3. *Students' behavior and understanding of the activities.* According to the teacher, their behavior was very good, and students clearly understood what had to be done.
4. *Learning with multilingual activities.* The three students realized that they could use other languages as a tool. They also appreciated that their first language, Spanish, could be useful in the learning process. These three immigrant students are separated from other students in the social science class taught in English, and the mathematics and physics classes taught in Basque because of their low level of English and Basque. According to the teacher, the students were happy to see that their Spanish was not an obstacle but a resource as it was useful to carry out this activity. Students thought that they learned more when working in three languages and that they also understood Basque better.
5. *Using pedagogical translanguageing in the future* because it can clarify some points.
6. Readiness of other teachers in your school to use pedagogical translanguageing.

It seems that some teachers already do that when they give students who have problems with English and Basque additional material in Spanish to introduce topics or reinforce the work they have done in class.

This school has implemented pedagogical translanguageing in a remedial class for a very specific purpose. The teacher has a clear focus on grammar and while this is not the official policy that encourages communicative activities, it is widespread. The postcard in three languages may provide opportunities for comparison but at the same time it may not be very challenging because students do not have information gaps and can get the information in Spanish. The remedial class, separating the three students from the rest of the class, seems to be part of the school policy and it also happens in other subjects.

3.8. School 3. multilingual news

Background information. This translanguageing experience took place in an English language class in the 2nd year of secondary school. The students are 13–14 years old. It is a public school and the main language instruction is Basque. The school is interested in the integration of the four languages that are offered at this level: Basque, Spanish, English and French.

The teacher has several years of experience teaching English. She is motivated and very open to learning new methodological approaches. There are 18 students in the class. The materials are related to other activities in the textbook which they use, but they have been developed specifically for this session by the teacher. The teaching unit in which the pedagogical translanguageing session was integrated is called "In the news". The students worked in groups. There were two groups of four students and two groups of five students. Three of the students had a lower level of English than the others. Two of these students are immigrant students with fewer years of instruction in English than local students and the other student has learning difficulties. These three students were in different groups.

Aim of pedagogical translanguageing. The specific aims of the session are to analyze the structure of the news, to listen, read and write some news, to discuss the news, to reflect on cognates and to develop awareness about different genres and registers.

3.9. Structure of the sessions

Part 1. Reading the news and identifying the structure. Each group was given newspapers in different languages and a piece of news in Spanish. Two students in each of the groups had to read the piece of news in Spanish and get ready to summarize the piece of news in Basque so as to provide the information to other students in the group. They were asked to change the language (Spanish to Basque) and also to change the genre from specialized written speech to everyday oral language. The other two or three students in the group were given another task. They had to analyze some of the news in the newspapers in different languages to identify the structure of the news items. The teacher guided them, pointing out the four most typical main parts of a piece of news:

Headline. It indicates the nature of the article and grabs the reader's attention.

Lead. It is the most important information. Who? What? Where? Why? When? How?

Body: It elaborates on the previous information. It can provide details and quotes and can analyze positive and negative aspects if relevant.

Tail: It provides additional information and is less important than the previous parts.

Students had to find examples of the typical structure of news items in the newspapers in different languages. Students reported their findings to the whole class.

Part 2. Listening to the news. Students were told that they would listen to the piece of news which they had first read in Spanish and that had been summarized orally in Basque. This time the language was going to be English. The teacher asked the students to brainstorm the words they expected to find in text they were about to listen to. Once they had listened to the item of news in English, they discussed the vocabulary they had guessed and then listened to it again but this time they read the text at the same time. The next activity was to find cognates from the news item in a chart, which was in English, Basque, Spanish and French. Students needed some help in their 4th language, French, and were allowed to use a dictionary.

Part 3 Writing the piece of news. Once students had finished identifying cognates, they were asked to write the news item in Basque using specialized written language. The teacher discussed the difference between the oral summary and the written text in Basque. One of the immigrant students wrote the news item in Arabic and read it to the whole class. The teacher asked the Basque language teacher to correct the Basque texts. In the next session, the teacher presented some digital newspapers and the students read the news in different languages.

3.10. Feedback from school 3

- 1 *Difficulty.* The students found the pedagogical translanguaging session easy but according to the teacher, some pointed out the difficulty of doing something different. Students felt confident because the piece of news they worked on was presented first in Spanish and Basque. The English text was more difficult for them.
- 2 *Teacher's feeling.* The teacher felt good doing something completely different from other classes. She enjoyed watching the students who were surprised by this class.
- 3 *Students' behavior and understanding of the activities.* Students were surprised at first but when they understood that they were working on four languages at the same time, they seemed to realize that the languages were not competing with each other but that they could, in fact, support each other. They really enjoyed this class.
- 4 *Learning with multilingual activities.* According to the teacher, students reported that they learned more because they could see the four languages together and they already knew the words in some languages. The teacher thinks that they developed metalinguistic awareness and they realized that languages are not separate compartments. However, the teacher finds it difficult to see if they learn more or less English this way because it was only one session.
- 5 *Using pedagogical translanguaging in the future.* The teacher explained that she already includes some multilingual exercises to ask students to translate or compare languages but just with very specific vocabulary or grammar points. After the success of the pedagogical translanguaging activity, she plans to include this type of session in the future.
- 6 *Readiness of other teachers in your school to use pedagogical translanguaging.*

The teacher thinks it could be possible and in fact she has already collaborated with the Basque language teacher.

The aim of the implementation of pedagogical translanguaging in School 3 was to use students' resources to understand and produce texts. Students could compare the structure of a specific genre, in this case journalistic texts, in three languages and even add a fourth one when working with vocabulary. The teacher also allows for the use of Arabic, the first language of one of the students, in the classroom.

4. Discussion

The implementation of pedagogical translanguaging in the three schools shows that even in situations with many shared characteristics, there are still some important differences. These three schools share the same core characteristics of pedagogical translanguaging regarding the type of program, the general aim of the translanguaging sessions, the organization with specifically planned activities and the approach with soft boundaries between languages. However, there are notable differences. Some differences may be linked to the fact that the first session took place in primary school, while the other two were in secondary schools. The pedagogical translanguaging implementation in primary school was carried out in the science class, while those in secondary took place in the English language classes. The science class in primary school was in the designated language, English, except for the exercise on cognates. This type of exercise puts into practice one of the descriptors of plurilingual comprehension in the CEFR Companion (Council of Europe, 2018: 160):

Can recognise similarities and contrasts between the way concepts are expressed in different languages, in order to distinguish between identical uses of the same word root and 'false friends'.

This type of activity goes further than simply developing comprehension in that it can also help to develop metalinguistic awareness and vocabulary in the three languages. Furthermore, an important remark made by the teacher is that during the implementation, more attention was devoted to language than in other science classes. It seems that pedagogical translanguaging can provide a better balance of language and content in a class when content subjects are taught through the medium of a second or foreign language.

The differences between the two secondary schools are quite striking. The focus in the second school was mainly on one grammatical structure, while the third school had a much broader focus on the characteristics of journalistic writing in different languages. The second school concentrated on language and was using direct translanguaging at the sentence level, whereas the third school was more oriented towards content and did not use direct translation. If we look at the CEFR Companion, the translanguaging activity carried out by school 2 matches the following descriptor (Council of Europe, 2018:160):

Can use his/her knowledge of contrasting grammatical structures and functional expressions of languages in his/her plurilingual repertoire in order to support comprehension.

The implementation of pedagogical translanguaging in school 3 matches several descriptors of the CEFR companion (Council of Europe, 2018: 160):

- Can use what he/she has understood in one language to understand the topic and main message of a text in another language.
- Can deduce the message of a text by exploiting what he/she has understood from texts on the same theme written in different languages (e.g. news in brief, museum brochure, online reviews).
- Can extract information from documents written in different languages in his/her field, e.g. to include in a presentation.
- Can use parallel translations of texts (e.g. magazine articles, stories, passages from novels) to develop comprehension in different languages.
- Can use his/her knowledge of contrasting genre conventions and textual pattern in languages in his/her plurilingual repertoire in order to support comprehension.

It can be seen that the three experiences match the descriptors but the teacher in school 3 applies translanguaging at the discourse level and focuses on different oral and written skills. Pedagogical translanguaging can take various shapes and these schools show some examples that can be extended in different directions, both in the Basque Country and in other contexts.

The three examples of pedagogical translanguaging share a common theme in that the whole linguistic repertoire is valued and used, not only the designated language of the class, which was English. Students are multilingual speakers who can use their multilingual resources to understand and complete different tasks (Cenoz & Gorter, 2015; García & Li, 2014; Lin, 2015). In this way, students not only understand better but also see that their multilingualism is valued. This can be seen clearly when primary school students are proud of their multilingualism in school 1 and also in the case of immigrant students when the Spanish speaking Latin American students find Spanish useful to learn English in school 2. The activities in school 3 show how pedagogical translanguaging is not limited to the languages in the curriculum and how other languages in the students' repertoire, such as Arabic in this case, can be valued as well.

The experience in the first school also shows the need to protect the minority language, Basque in this case, when pedagogical translanguaging is implemented. The teacher in school 1 refers to this concern when she reflects on the possibility of extending pedagogical translanguaging to other classes. This shows the need to protect minority languages when pedagogical translanguaging is implemented (Cenoz & Gorter, 2017).

This study shows how pedagogical translanguaging is implemented but it is limited to one teacher and one classroom in each of the schools. Pedagogical translanguaging could be more effective if several teachers or the whole school participated. Otherwise, the potential risk is that the extensive use of three or more languages only in one class, for example in the English language class, could result in less exposure to a language that is not strong in the community. This is not a problem if pedagogical translanguaging is used in the other language classes or in content classes because the more limited exposure of one language in one school subject can be compensated for in the other classes. This is a challenge for the implementation of pedagogical translanguaging at the school level because it implies coordination among teachers, professional development courses and the development of pedagogical translanguaging materials for different subjects. This challenge is not easy to respond to because of the strength of traditional language separation ideologies (García & Lin, 2017). However, there is a real need to focus on multilingualism and to soften the boundaries between languages when teaching in multilingual education because it can be more effective and also because it reflects the way multilingual speakers use their resources (Cenoz & Gorter, 2011, 2015).

The results of this study show that pedagogical translanguaging can take different shapes even in contexts that share many characteristics. At the same time, the study shows how students can be encouraged to use their multilingual repertoire so as to raise metalinguistic awareness and benefit from their own multilingualism.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Basque Government under Grant DREAM IT-1225-19.

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